

DPIK: User Embodiment of Dual-point Tracked Avatars Using Hand IK and Face Tracking for Smartphone AR Users (Appendix)

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July 28, 2025

1 Supplemental Material

1.1 Rotational Error Statistics

Here we present the rotational error statistics per joint per axis for both ARIKA and DPIK (Table 1). We highlight the lower mean difference in the individual joints to better visualize the difference between ARIKA and DPIK. For details on our analysis, please refer to section 5.1 Euclidean Distance & Rotational Errors in our paper.

We present comparative visualizations in Figure 1 and Figure 2 to illustrate the rotational error differences between ARIKA and DPIK. A notable observation is that the Right Wrist, which corresponds to the hand holding the smartphone, exhibits the highest standard deviation, despite having a relatively low mean rotational error. Furthermore, the rotational error patterns between ARIKA and DPIK are almost similar for the Right Wrist. This can be attributed to the shared approach both systems use for hand IK which works by snapping the avatar’s hand to the smartphone’s digital representation, without accounting for the user’s exact grip or hand pose. In contrast, OptiTrack, the motion capture system, provides a more precise measurement of hand orientation, leading to discrepancies that are not fully resolved by the IK approximation.

Table 1: Mean(M) and standard deviation(SD) of the rotational error per axis for ARIKA and DPIK

Joint	(a) ARIKA						(b) DPIK					
	Pitch		Yaw		Roll		Pitch		Yaw		Roll	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Chest	10.280	9.584	18.241	24.040	2.533	8.809	9.405	9.182	17.698	23.747	2.128	8.383
Head	-14.977	14.679	7.765	18.346	-0.569	8.575	-11.768	7.767	6.397	10.722	0.346	4.759
Hips	2.122	6.236	10.431	25.729	2.116	5.639	2.556	6.523	9.913	25.581	2.053	5.898
Left Ankle	-8.927	8.622	-4.463	14.619	2.783	26.371	-8.057	8.383	-4.834	14.634	2.897	26.657
Left Clavicle	17.910	4.539	-9.875	6.392	-16.314	26.840	17.897	4.451	-9.052	5.569	-15.860	26.593
Left Elbow	4.386	17.915	9.474	36.854	28.729	34.231	4.051	18.495	10.516	36.415	29.244	33.627
Left Hip Joint	2.343	12.395	-19.149	23.817	6.849	10.114	-0.029	13.201	-20.024	24.319	6.698	10.621
Left Knee	5.732	10.673	-16.062	23.977	-3.927	12.110	7.394	10.515	-16.767	24.459	-5.101	12.379
Left Shoulder	19.612	10.534	-6.193	26.084	-0.598	22.700	19.142	9.766	-5.986	25.824	0.825	21.944
Left Wrist	14.430	30.547	4.640	38.149	34.148	39.517	14.381	28.320	6.008	36.996	34.842	36.910
Neck	4.574	8.914	17.342	19.959	7.879	8.466	3.886	9.065	18.123	19.605	-9.058	8.999
Right Ankle	-10.673	9.488	-4.958	15.626	8.998	22.658	-9.173	8.625	-3.970	15.232	7.598	22.024
Right Clavicle	11.477	10.204	8.723	6.430	-20.457	25.701	14.383	10.350	7.906	5.888	-18.890	24.879
Right Elbow	9.862	36.948	-17.815	38.572	-20.451	40.281	-6.713	41.063	-17.324	36.559	-7.704	45.999
Right Hip Joint	4.732	12.816	-2.090	27.626	-5.417	8.822	2.201	12.002	-0.843	27.054	-4.623	8.098
Right Knee	5.804	9.977	0.047	25.282	-6.325	12.564	7.258	9.907	1.078	25.340	-5.269	12.555
Right Shoulder	-11.678	14.379	5.701	18.759	8.943	21.837	-15.811	17.958	1.313	16.035	3.743	18.662
Right Wrist	9.809	99.916	-19.286	23.867	-71.048	62.627	9.656	99.647	-19.341	23.864	-70.995	62.079
Spine	13.668	10.007	15.976	23.923	6.9255	9.759	13.128	9.757	15.327	23.692	6.644	9.754

(a) Pitch

(b) Yaw

(c) Roll

Figure 1: Comparison of the rotational error between ARIKA and DPIK per axis across right and left joints.

(a) Pitch

(b) Yaw

(c) Roll

Figure 2: Comparison of the rotational error between ARIKA and DPIK per axis across center joints.